

DIGITAL ILLITERACY AND ITS SOCIO-EDUCATIONAL IMPACTS

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ABSTRACT

Digital illiteracy is a problem that affects a range of individuals at all educational and social levels, because it is not a question of being in possession of technodigital consumer goods, but of mastery of the technique on the handling, possibilities and potential offered by the technological innovations related to information and communication, access to the world-wide network of computers and other production processes, generated by the technical-scientific advances from the second half of the 20th century and beginning of the 21st century. It is a bibliographical research based on empirical observation, especially in basic and higher education environments. The general objective is to solve the conflict between digital illiteracy and digital exclusion, explaining that the former is characterized as the absence of dominance and the second, it is a euphemism because the person who changes is the society and the individual immersed in it suffers its direct impacts, being included in the digital age as a direct consequence of sociological advances. This is an issue that needs to be clarified so that the processes of promoting positive public policies to serve the public are of an effective character and not merely ideological.

Keywords: Digital illiteracy; Information and communication technologies; Socio-educational impacts; It was tick.

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century has provided many fantastic advances, including the era of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), in which [*almost*] everything became, more or less

abruptly, computerized, with greater speed in circulation and exchanges of information, a fact that can thus be called the *ICT ERA* ¹².

As is natural to occur, every scientific advance, which ends up having a direct impact on the sociological field, brings with it ingrained innumerable challenges, which demand from scientists and researchers an [almost] immediate response, giving *rise* to many discussions and many speculations, which do not respond to the anxieties of the population, causing the emergence of more questions and more challenges, which in this particular case, the technical advances and the opportunity to access new conquests, in an increasingly short time, produce a form of satisfaction for all, even if your questions have not been answered satisfactorily. Its real need ends up anesthetized by the market novelty which, due to the fact that it does not master it, considers it essential.

The growth of man in the 21st century, in the *ICT ERA* , brought with it a new form of social exclusion, caused by digital illiteracy, which, however much one seeks an interpretation, does not reach an understanding of the reason for its existence, as if there were a magic formula that would distance everyone who claims to be included in the digital world of the *poltergeist* from the mechanical ignorance that this era advocated for human beings. There is a whole market juggling to ensure that the consumer-user does not reach the level of excellence in knowledge and mastery over the technique, which is not a technique, but a new device that obeys more complex commands, capable of performing a wider range of objective functions.

This is the nerve of the situation, in which the word *illiteracy* and the adjective *illiterate* have become violent and abject forms of reference to anyone, something as if such expressions had been elevated to the status of *sociological taboo* . ¹³This puerile and infantile belief is due to two perspectives disconnected from human existential reality, in which all life and existence came to be determined by euphemisms: in the first case, the individual is not illiterate; he just does not yet know the mechanisms that allow him to dominate the means of access and production of material goods and, in the second case, there are the ideologues on duty who, following the Platonic mystique, are convinced that the simple fact of living in a computerized era and that machines are present in [*almost*] all spaces of human action, this is enough to

¹² CANIÇALI, MNSA; SOUZA, MR. The *teaching place* as an epistemological foundation of the pedagogical praxis in the ICT ERA. *Anais do II International Congress on Education and Technologies*. São Carlos: Federal University of São Carlos, 2018.

¹³ The term *taboo* (*tapu*) comes from the Polynesian language, which means something sacred, special, forbidden, dangerous or unclean. *Taboo* is a concept used in philosophy, anthropology and sociology and is related to the prohibition, censorship, danger and impurity of certain social activities . It supports discussions with controversial themes, generally discriminated against by society, from customs, religions, sexual options, lifestyle, among others.

make human beings literate creatures in informatics matters and in the mechanisms of the virtual world, such as access, mediation, manipulation and domain.

Digital illiteracy is characterized as the lack of mastery in the fields of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), which can be categorized as the absence of a minimum mastery of use and access to technological information up to the conditions of sophisticated mastery, depending on the degree of demand of the individual's work environment. Let it be clarified that, at the speed with which new computer software is developed, ignorance in handling and in full control of products that are launched on the market becomes a very definite mark in the process.

Based on what has been exposed, pedagogical action and public policies to combat this problem (digital illiteracy) involve broader opportunities for access to the technological components of mass information and communication, teacher training, insertion in the curricula of higher education courses of mandatory training elements and domains in ICT's, not only learning to handle the *software*, but also learning to think about the digital inclusion processes, so that they promote combat, in an efficient and effective way against this bad.

A detail to be highlighted is that knowing how to use the tool is not enough; it is necessary to know how to determine when its use improves the answers to be achieved. The mere fact of gaining time in certain productions is not a guarantee of quality or safety in technical processes. When addressing the literacy element here, it has been clarified that the authors take it as a form of mastery over the technique in question. Education is something that presumes a relationship of reciprocity and simultaneity between theory and practice, understanding by this thought that it is a praxis, a concept that is based on and from a scientific process that, when thought and expressed in another way than not this one, it cannot be defined as something that is justified, by itself. Many theorists, flattered by the advances achieved by the sciences and dumbed down by their own vanity, have forgotten [*for convenience or ignorance*] that the epistemological formation of a human being goes through the accompaniment of a qualified professional, considering that even the most audacious and promising, if left to its own devices, will produce chimeras and other flashy things with a tendency to believe that it is producing something wonderful and innovative.¹⁴

A literate individual can be considered as such from the moment he acquires and expresses the ability to encode and decode the linguistic signs that permeate, form and compose his culture. Before there was a literate culture represented by spelling, there was no need to

¹⁴In this regard, see BACON, Francis. *Novum organum or the New Atlantis*. So Paulo: Nova Cultural, 2000.

separate literate and illiterate concepts; However, with the emergence of writing, in addition to the symbolic elements that made the expression of thought possible, the need for individuals to know how to decode and interpret these same elements emerges. This was necessary for there to be a dynamic and dialectical process of communication, understood as symbolic expression by one individual and lucid understanding by another(s).

This initial reflection serves as a parameter for understanding that once a paradigm is established, it becomes the *leitmotiv* of the situation, that is, it begins to dictate the rules on how all other elements will be considered, within a given field of action, from then on. and this serves as a clarification that digital illiteracy is a paradigm, not necessarily a problem that directly affects everyone, as people would like to believe. And digital illiteracy is the strongest paradigm of the 21st Century that was elaborated from the emergence of digital tools and the insertion of the world in an era where things respond more through pressing buttons, as if this represented the *quintessence* and the indelible mark of human historical evolution.

Another complicating factor in this game system of interpreting linguistic variants is that digital inclusion is not the same as combating digital illiteracy. In no known place, there was still the much publicized digital inclusion, in an equitable way and, to make matters worse, it is not enough to include in the school curricula all the teaching parameters related to ICTs, in the puerile belief that this will prove to be an object capable of solving a problem, because it only creates another, more acute and profound one, since not even the schools are using their computer labs anymore and the sacred question remains: 'How is an individual going to learn the notions of basic information technology and advanced, without ever having access to the components of a computer?'

Literacy is a process that refers to a praxis, to an action that requires an equal relationship of reciprocity and simultaneity between theory and practice. The euphemism was created that *everyone has* the latest generation cell phones, tablets and other marvels of computer engineering, which is just a decoy and an unreasonable idea. The fact is that, if the school is a place of education, training, integration, it is up to it to provide the right balance between theory and practice and not adhere to an ideological rhetorical discourse based on euphemisms.

It becomes very interesting the idea of fighting digital illiteracy in human beings who don't even know what a computer is, who have never seen one of these wonders and, possibly, there are many individuals who will never be introduced to them. Every proposal must be based on the real need posed by the challenging situation. When addressing the problem of lack of knowledge and mastery of ICTs, the aim is not only to teach how to handle the machine and its

electronic resources, but how to use it in the most technical way possible, enjoying it in the most intelligent, culminating in interpretations that, as a direct result, will produce knowledge, solid learning products.

When addressing the issue of combating digital illiteracy, one should think about developing the education and comprehensive training of these individuals, so that their cognitive and intellectual development does not allow itself to be guided outside the principles of ethics and conduct based on the organization of a society that seeks the maximum development of its potential. Someone who learns to master ICT tools is of no use if all of their learning ends up being directed towards achievements that will not help in the construction of a fair [*or less unfair*] and solidary society.

Heated speeches against or in favor of the State or the government are not enough, because this does not help to solve the problem that arises, since the emergence of problematic situations that challenge the understanding of things are a consequence of the evolutionary process, in which first the technical-scientific novelty appears, then, as a consequence, the need to train individuals for the proper use of this product arises, because, otherwise, it would be a useless technology, which does not meet the demands of a world and a society. pragmatic society.

With this, we have that, before the emergence of information and communication technologies (ICT), it was enough for the individual to know how to read and write for him to be considered included in the literate culture. It was not considered that this same individual would be excluded from literate culture even if he was literate; this would sound like something ridiculous, unthinkable. However, with the entry of humanity into the *ICT ERA*, the concept of *digital literacy emerges* , which becomes [*almost*] automatically into a paradigm; therefore, anyone who is not or is not digitally literate is, by analogy, a digital illiterate.

Therefore, a digital illiterate is one who, even knowing how to read and write, codify the letters of their culture, does not have mastery of machines or digital tools such as computers and programs (software), because, with technological advances, it becomes essential *for* the routine, such as knowing how to use bank machines (ATMs) to withdraw money and other tasks. In this way, it is necessary to create a product that meets this demand for mass qualification of individuals who, directly and indirectly, found themselves inserted in the computerized world and dominated by the *ICT ERA* .

This action is justified by the pertinence of the theme regarding the need to intervene in a problem that does not tend to be solved, but rather to expand, because the world has become increasingly technified, more technological, more sophisticated in its actions of promotion and

development of virtual communication techniques. Along with all of this, there are changes taking place in formal educational environments, such as the implementation of electronic guidelines in schools, *online diaries*, active methodologies, computerization of teaching and learning processes, which awakens the pressing need for teachers to be connected with these didactic and methodological advances that come together with the new procedures enabling an authentic and autonomous insertion of humanity in the *ICT ERA*.

Taking the above exposure as a problem to be faced, this book is justified by the pertinence of the theme regarding the need for intervention in a problem that does not tend to be solved, but rather to expand, because the world has become increasingly technified, more technological, more sophisticated in its actions to promote and develop virtual communication techniques, in contrast to the conditions of access offered to students and teachers in the public education network.

DIGITAL ILLITERACY AND ITS DIRECT AND INDIRECT CONSEQUENCES

Digital illiteracy is characterized as an evil that arises from the entry of the contemporary world into the *ICT ERA*¹⁵, that is, when a computerized vision takes over social thinking and this becomes a real obstacle, if not, an obstacle to the socioeconomic growth.

The most serious mistake that has been made when trying to deal with digital illiteracy is to think that it is linked to the lowest level of wisdom in the use of digital instruments and that fighting it is a task that demands effort and political good will, enabling individuals to access technological goods, such as cell phones, tablets and personal computers. The understanding and understanding of these senses become much more complex, because human curiosity is something that does not know any kind of limit and technical-technological evolution, especially in recent times, has faced human thought and desire as a limit, little or nothing else. Thus, it is exposed that the fact of learning to handle a computer or other tool, paying bills *online*, accessing forums, *chats* and other situations are no longer guarantees that the individual is digitally literate [*in its full conception*] and that if your curiosity or desire to go beyond this knowledge challenges you to do so, you will discover that there is another level of literacy that will demand the same or greater effort from you than when you started on your journey of learning the most basic concepts and differently, of vernacular languages, that one

¹⁵ CANIÇALI, MNSA; SOUZA, MR. *The teaching place as an epistemological foundation of the pedagogical praxis in the ICT ERA. Anais do II International Congress on Education and Technologies*. São Carlos: Federal University of São Carlos, 2018.

day you reach the point of being an expert, being able to say of yourself that you are a genius, that you no longer know a language limit that no longer has reach, digital technologies challenge anyone, because the new functions arise for them every moment and these are adapted to other systems of thought, increasingly complex and demanding [very] unique structures of interpretation.

When taking this line of understanding of the problem of digital literacy, this idea is more linked to an era, to a time and that can no longer be retrogressed anywhere, because the ideal formations of advances in all sectors of life, are somehow interconnected by these systems, which are gradually demanding new structures of thoughts and worldviews, aware that all idealists, strategists and entrepreneurs are that there is no way to keep an innovative idea long removed from popular knowledge. And in this century, they are not even so concerned with keeping technical-digital discoveries and inventions hidden, because they have already discovered that even if the majority has unrestricted access to them, there are odd functions to which the attention of the overwhelming majority will be attracted, not affecting the natural order of things.

Here fits the role of the school, which is to teach students to become conscious users and make rational use of the available digital instruments. Being digitally literate, in this sense, means being able to systematically, conscientiously, pragmatically and ethically explore the best that digital technology can offer for the common good, being useful to the greatest possible number of individuals. Many apparently broad projects end up doomed to failure because they do not present, in their composition, a useful purpose for what is learned, always remaining in the abstract discourse of inclusion. The average citizen is not interested in this, he wants his efforts to learn something beyond himself to be compensated with some financial return or self-esteem. The majority of the population ignores this digital illiterate jargon, and what they really want is to be able to enjoy the benefits and potential of digital technologies, as they wish.

According to Almeida, “a person who does not master the computer and its tools is considered digitally illiterate, which nowadays is considered as important as knowing how to read and write” , ¹⁶because life has become governed by more complex processes, in which digital technologies have strongly marked the ways of being and living, of each citizen and of society as a whole.

This suggests the adoption of measures that directly reflect on the eradication of this disease, serving a population that is on the margins of the computerized society, however, which

¹⁶ALMEIDA, MEB. Management of technologies, media and resources at school: sharing meanings. *In Aberto* , Brasilia, v. 22, no. 79, p. 75-89, Jan. 2009.

is not outside the technological world, which may seem a paradox, but which concentrates the idea that the world has become digitized and people have not been able, by force majeure, to add their lives to these paradigm shifts and neither have governments, capable of inserting everyone into this system, through efficient public policies and effective.

They directed the solution of the problem to schools and teachers, but they forgot that the former obeys a rigid standard, a system that is developed outside its walls and is inserted in it, and it is up to it to comply with it, without much questioning. and without ample liberty to alter it; reference is made here to the curriculum. And the latter, as much as they seem to have good will and this is not real, nor enough to change the meaning of things in the world, most of them lack a more solid formation, in which they could put to the test, everything that it is dictated as a new reality by [*supposed*] thinkers of education.

Due to this lack of critical-analytical thinking on the part of those who directly take care of the teaching and learning processes, it has become common to believe in the idea that being connected in networks is a *conditio sine qua non* to be *considered* a digitally literate. It is understood, therefore, that “technologies today permeate various sectors of society, such as schools, public sectors, hospitals, commerce, among others. When we go to the bank, to the cinema, to the airport, for example, we are somehow dealing with digital networks. Currently, for example, buying on the Internet, reading a book on a tablet and chatting through social networks on a cell phone are common habits of those who live in the information society.”¹⁷

Not everyone is at this level [*of desire*] for literacy and it is necessary to consider the opportunities presented and the availability of each individual to learn to handle and explore media resources. Myopia is found in the fact that, in most schools in large centers, which is the furthest where researchers risk going, there is a high range of students carrying state-of-the-art cell phones and seem to master something, when the most they can do with these devices is play games and send messages. They do not master the constellations of game development, ideas, software, they do not even know how to properly search for books, reliable electronic sites, research manuals, technical dictionaries and other instruments that will enable them to have a technical-scientific humanistic formation more accurate and competent and the most aggravating thing is that their professors, like them, do not know even for themselves, much less to guide their students, which produces a real problem, in which digital illiteracy ceases to be factual. to assume a virtual character.

¹⁷VILAÇA MLC; ARAUJO EVF. (ORG.). *Technology, society and education in the digital age*. Duque de Caxias: Unigranrio, 2016, p. 21.

To give a concept to something is to insert it in a context, in a paradigm, if not, to create a paradigm for it, a way that other scientists can address such an element, giving it an identity condition. A condition of being or not being can lead to several others, which unfold in chains and form pre-concepts and post-concepts, more or less true, about how contacts are established between the possibilities and potentialities that each situation confers on individuals. Therefore, starting from the premise that the illiterate condition, in any modality, is liable to trigger problems and difficulties of all kinds.

What is sought with this narrative is the transparency of the idea that there is a need to understand that “to be considered digitally included, it is not enough to have a computer and be connected to the internet; to be considered included, guidance is needed, teaching in the correct way and how to benefit from this technology.”¹⁸

It is necessary to clarify and it is never less to say that, more than a proposal for digital inclusion, it is necessary to have a measure that helps in the political solution of digital illiteracy that attacks everyone, at all socioeconomic and educational levels, not doing the slightest distinction; however, those who are, by political and economic nature, on the margins of society are the ones who suffer the most direct impacts. They claim that it is the role of education and the school, but when teachers are unprepared to meet this demand or when the school barely has electricity, or even more aggravating, when school units in urban centers have computer labs that cannot be used because of political decisions, it remains unclear what role this and teachers can play in promoting real digital inclusion and how to minimize the impacts of digital illiteracy on students and, consequently, on their families, because once these children learned at school could transmit something to their parents and grandparents, helping them with shopping in supermarkets and using ATMs.

The changes that have occurred in the world, especially in the last thirty years, have given rise to a wave of fear and when this occurs, the tendency is for the formation of an internal resistance that prevents great advances from happening and that other achievements can endorse the annals of human history. What may seem like a natural thing for children, is not for adults, because as the former did not know anything before arriving at school and being inserted into life in a pragmatic way, what they see as a teaching proposal is understood as something natural, which has always been there, making no difference to your world; contrary to what happens with the adult, who needs to adopt such a thing as being new and challenging, because he spent

¹⁸Sousa A. *Computers and the digital divide*. (2. Ed.). Dourados: Independently published, 2017, p. 11.

his whole life without that particular concept and now he has to add it to his life, his routine, changing it, greatly .

This unique condition of human beings makes it clear that dealing with the problem of digital illiteracy implies analyzing human nature in its deepest nuances in order to make it possible to draw up action plans and goals for the short, medium and long term. How to achieve the proposed objectives is always a challenge that involves efficient planning and must be based on effective didactics.

Thus, the digital literacy process includes a broad pedagogical work, in which the objectives must be planned with a view to promoting a process, starting from a basic model to a complex model, elaborated on epistemological bases and attitudinal characteristics. Thus, we have that, “digital inclusion when taken literally is the most ideal, qualified and ungodly artifice to combat social exclusion and digital exclusion, but only if digital inclusion with computers, internet access and forms and programs to qualify and initiate computer science in the sense of adequate learning regarding the use of this technology in their favor.”¹⁹

For this situation of promoting digital literacy to be consolidated as a public policy of effective action, it is necessary to invest in the revision of academic curricula and in the computer labs of regular schools, because being connected in a network is not yet a reality for the the majority of students and not even for the population in general, which leads to another difficulty, which is to enable individuals to know all the systematic development of logical-abstract thinking, involving the use of digital technologies.

What is sought here is the condition that literacy implies promoting advances in the aspect of analysis, understanding, interpretation, understanding and synthesis of the elements that make up the entire process of formation of ideas that conflict and converge for the ideal formation of educational systems . In this way, digital literacy would imply providing people with new ways of seeing the world in all its potential and based on the conditions of intellectual-cognitive development that involve the evolutionary processes of all formal society. This is a type of action that takes a very long time, because in order to reach the minimum conditions for providing epistemological access to digital instruments and these allowing the user to reach the epistemological scope, another era of challenges is about to come, the judging that not everyone is at the threshold of learning necessary for that, due to several factors [*endogenous and exogenous*], such as basic education, poverty factors, access to consumer goods, capacity and basic intellectual development, ability and competence and personal interest.

¹⁹Sousa A. *Computers and the digital divide*. (2. Ed.). Dourados: Independently published, 2017, p. 49.

This being the case, what is actually necessary for someone to come to consider himself or be considered digitally literate? This, which seems to be a rhetorical question, holds a frightening and immeasurable depth, starting with the fact that no answer would be equal to the problem, considering that anyone who dares to claim that he has reached his highest and [presumably] degree of digital literacy would be *stating*, categorically, that no innovative and unknown invention of himself would appear in the world until the moment of his death.

However, what is questioned and highlighted in this situation is the ability to continue adapting to innovations and, with this, rising to an ever greater degree of knowledge, wisdom, mastery and improvement of the technique, seeking a fair balance between *episteme* and *phrónesis*, considering that being literate is a principle, being able to keep up with changes, evolutions and innovations in the technological world is a necessity, and that, on the other hand, this condition does not cover everyone, for several reasons reasons, more or less profound. And it is these problematic challenges that education and the Academy have to face, as a way of expanding citizen participation in the processes of digital inclusion and combating and [*possible*] eradication of digital illiteracy.

Following this same line of argument, Sousa emphasizes that, “if the problems of education do not accompany technological development and if based on it to improve, it is not just the lack of a computer per student, the qualification of teachers is also reflected in this, the public and private universities today and in the past do not offer and did not offer in their curriculum subjects that aim to prepare or insert the teacher in the technological world, however it does not apply to all, some have these subjects, but in a non-mandatory way that in return does not attract academics.”²⁰

This suggests the perception that much more than a lack of public policies, there is a lack of interest in solving the problem of digital illiteracy, which is not limited to complete ignorance about the use of electronic instruments linked to ICTs, to lack of mastery sophisticated or in order to meet the needs posed by each specific system, it is configured as a different level of digital illiteracy which, however, does not cease to be. Of all this, what can be seen, as a fact, are the immeasurable losses of opportunities for socioeconomic advances, marked by this evil that affects today's society.

Again, it must be emphasized here that digital illiteracy as a social problem is an academic euphemism, because the common man, the citizen who has his life based on daily

²⁰SOUSA, A. *Computers and the digital divide*. (2. Ed.). Dourados: Independently published, 2017, p. 51.

work, wants, at most, to know how to properly use technological tools for his pleasure individual, not to make the world a nicer or more dangerous place.

One cannot disregard the idea that learning about the use of software, nowadays, is something as relevant as learning Mathematics, Portuguese Language and Science, but that this will not change the life story of [almost] anyone, like masters the vernacular letters. Thought must be directed to the understanding that at this exact moment in human political history, not being digitally literate is running the risk of remaining, even more, on the sidelines of technical and social advances.

DIGITAL ILLITERACY AND ITS SOCIO-EDUCATIONAL IMPACTS

Illiteracy affects all branches of intellectual knowledge, being a fact and denominated until recently in relation to writing and reading and, even within its scope, it has been gaining new configurations, because as society has become more demanding in terms of mastering the vernacular language and its principles, new scopes have emerged and new classifications for the term have been endorsed by the academic community.

When ICTs appear and they are kept at the margins of society, there was no reason to say that those who did not know them and, moreover, who did not dominate them could be considered as illiterates in this respect, earning them the denomination of digital *illiterates*. However, as they are added to everyday life, with the need for conditions for a minimum domain of their properties, and as a way of offering opportunities to the largest number of individuals, education assumes this social responsibility, however, it adds to its entourage of values to consider anyone who does not have a minimum command of ICT tools, as a digital illiterate and even so, this classification is quite flexible, because with each module of performance and advancement that the student achieves, he does not cease to be an illiterate digital, considering that, like what happened with vernacular languages that were being transformed into instruments of power, domination and exclusion, ICTs suffer from the same process and with each scientific advance achieved, further away from a situation of absolute domination the student stays. It is a known fact that in contemporary times, new challenges have been posed to society and among these, one of the greatest impact is the need for individuals to master information technology. This is not always a reality in the educational environment, due to several factors, highlighting the students' lack of financial resources and entrepreneurship, teachers' proactivity and this condition of ignorance of didactic-pedagogical

processes related to Information and Communication Technologies (ICT's).), lead to educational results far below what is desirable and below what would be possible.

What [*almost*] nobody wants to be aware of is the fact that digital inclusion and access to techno-digital consumer goods are very different things, not making any parallel with one another. With the advent of the Digital Information and Communication Era, everyone, without distinction, was included in the technological era and in its modes of production, consumption, services, etc. What has not been resolved is the problem of excluding the individual from free and broad access to technological goods and another paradox is that, once their access to them is guaranteed and provided, it also does not guarantee, under any circumstances, that they are digitally literate.

Every problem is involved in a problematic and this is a dimension that cannot be thought outside of a political order, because it involves systems of thought, far beyond providing miraculous solutions, it involves decisions at the level of curriculum adjustment, formal teaching proposals, adjustment of disciplines, pedagogical intervention, didactic intervention and the direct and indirect movement of human and financial resources, in which the former need to be trained, to adapt to the teaching and learning programs.

At the same time, it is necessary to adapt the speech to the students who arrive at school, because talking about acquiring computers for those who are hungry at home is a very low blow. Therefore, it is necessary to teach these children how to use digital tools and machines and draw up service plans so that they can, in the extracurricular period, deepen their knowledge and continue to seek conditions for viable market opportunities at the level of their dream of life. It is not through heated speeches that those who do not master digital tools will be out of the job market that students' attention will be attracted to this branch of knowledge, because they all know someone in the family or close to them who cannot even read and write and is very well.

It must always be borne in mind that the child has a very low degree of abstraction and, therefore, interventions must be carried out with the maximum of a didactic character, so that they can feel attracted to the problem and assume part of the responsibility for its solution.

It should be clarified that, when talking about digital illiteracy, we have a pedagogical view of the problem raised by the insertion of ICTs in the educational world. On the other hand, when talking about digital inclusion, the problem is approached from a sociological perspective, in which its solution involves improving living conditions, access to consumer goods, purchasing power. Digital illiteracy is at the level of individual will, wanting to overcome the condition of minority, wanting to overcome the dichotomous barriers of having and being,

which once overcome, promotes the condition of knowing, of being able to interpret, which, in the conception of Jaspers, leads to knowledge, since, in his conception, every action of interpretation leads to the autonomous capacity to produce knowledge, which, in turn, is a product of learning.²¹

Thus, it can be said that when thinking about mechanisms to face and eradicate digital illiteracy, the proposal should be to provide students with epistemological advances so that they can become autonomous in their intellectual constructions and that they know how to make the most of , the learning situations that technological tools make available. For this reason, to state that, “it is not enough to have a didactic space, one must bear in mind that those who occupy it must be sufficiently prepared to contribute with valid knowledge, or taking K. Jaspers' conception, be able to interpret reality in such a way that it translates into useful knowledge for the entire scientific community.”²²

What can be understood from these authors' statements is that the solution to the problem, for which there is no short-term solution, because it involves different actions that permeate political actions to facilitate access to consumer goods and structural changes in the curriculum cannot be thought out and executed without this having an impact on the lives of citizens and even this impact must be calculated, so that it does not end up as another phantom investment, in which no one benefits from it, or that it is a social decoy .

In order to expand the possibilities for solving this problem, one should think about a solid formation of the basic teacher, the one who works with the little ones, in the Education of the Initial Years of Elementary School, because it already has the possibility of preparing them to think abstractly, from direct contact with digital technologies and all their possibilities and potential. What is sought, in the *ICT ERA* , is not a rare and unknown type of knowledge, the desire is to set in motion a whole way of promoting the expansion of thinking, creating solid links between concrete thinking and abstract thinking, reaching the logical ways of doing high science. This does not imply that when the individual stops being a digital illiterate, he can become an expert, as if this happened by magic or enchantment; the idea is to enable the construction of concrete ideals of a society in which it expands its ways of rebuilding it from the handling of its technological tools.

²¹ JASPERS, K. *Philosophy*. 11. Ed. Mexico: Fund for Economic Culture, 1991.

²² CANIÇALI, MNSA; SOUZA, MR. *El teaching place as an epistemological foundation of the pedagogical praxis in the ICT ERA. Anais do II International Congress on Education and Technologies*. São Carlos: Federal University of São Carlos, 2018, p. 53.

What cannot be accepted in the knowledge society are professors who do not know or who refuse to know, because as these are the driving springs on which the new generation bases itself and bases its life proposals, the fact of not being engaged in the technological society, even in a rudimentary way, which would already be absurd, implies an unprecedented setback. We are not saying that the teacher should be connected for the sake of being connected, or to show himself to be modern in front of his students, but so that he can get to know the paths and detours of the tools, the dangers and challenges posed by them, and thus, have the capacity to guide, as equitably as possible, their students.

Furthermore, a digitally illiterate teacher is a deadly contagious disease for the process of teaching and training thinking minds, critical of the process, because despite depriving their students of contact with the latest technological tools, they will still try to persuade them to who can live and well without them, using himself and everything he has achieved as an example. With this speech, he motivates his students to be less, to risk an already retrograde process in a world that advances at a speed [*almost*] unreachable by new thinking heads.

This situation calls attention to the training and didactic preparation of teachers, especially those who work directly with students in the early years, who depend on a solid foundation to learn to walk alone and autonomously when they reach the final years of school. primary and secondary education. In addition to having to reach this level, the final stage of Basic Education with consolidated knowledge, it is necessary to know how to analyse, understand, understand and synthesize the digital and digitized world that is placed in front of it, with which it must have affinity and dialogue at the time. of its epistemic, didactic and sociological requirements.

Anything thought and executed outside of this bias creates what is called an ideological culture, in which you have an idea that, at first glance, seems to be wonderful, but which is not sustainable due to the fact that it does not provide any kind of sustainable advancement to individuals. that make direct or indirect use of it and the same happens with the school that does not invest in structuring its curriculum not thinking about the society we live in, which is already highly complex and with a high rate of difficulties to be overcome, even by those who can say with [*relative*] certainty that they have the means to face the challenges posed without any concern.

When thinking about the curriculum and a widely publicized discourse in schools at all levels is that it comes ready-made and canned from higher bodies, leaving nothing more to the teacher than to execute it and this, in itself, is a fallacy, because there is a percentage of 30% in which the school and the teachers can organize according to the demand that is more urgent in

the attendance of the students. Of course, with only abstract teaching and the impossibility of teaching the contents and modes of operation of information technology and other ICT mechanisms through practical classes, this does very little to reduce or even minimize the effective numbers and the [*direct and indirect*] impacts of digital illiteracy.

The most interesting thing is that this is a unique moment in human history, because the type of technological development that is now being experienced, in fact, cannot be compared with anything that has ever been seen before, which makes it treated with respect and with a certain dose of fear, provoking different levels of resistance. This, in a way, is healthy, because it forces philosophers to seek more objective answers to the problems that are posed and in this, a portion of the population that would remain marginalized ends up being involved in the process, awakening social awareness to the problem that is much greater than the possibilities of resolving it, ignoring the groups of actors who can make a difference in the fight against this new type of social confrontation.

Never in human history has history taught man so much about how to act in his present. When precedents are sought and nothing is found to support them, this is the moment when it offers its greatest instructional legacy, steeped in intellectuality and epistemic possibilities, because it allows human beings to discover themselves in the face of the challenge of thinking about their present. , from the silence of his past and in this process, he becomes a producer and creator of knowledge that will serve as support for his [*uncertain and dark*] future. Never at any time in human history has it been advocated that someone literate and literate could return to a condition of ignorance such that they would be classified as illiterate and such a condition would be able to exclude them from the processes of social advances. This unique situation both amazes and enchants him, because it puts him at the forefront of seeking a solution to an evil that arises as a consequence of what was advocated and conventionally called evolution, in the midst of the era of knowledge and intellectual capital. . Digital illiteracy can be characterized as the most paradoxical paradox of this human age.

CONCLUSION

Approaching the concept of digital illiteracy has become complex, because it is very easily perceived that it is not a concept, the reference is directly linked to a theoretical principle, because we are no longer talking about having or not having access to the instruments digital and a highly technological and virtual world, because everyone, in rare conditions, is connected

to it and under its domain. The fact of having access and consummation of the fluent domain of teaching and learning techniques of digital tools is being addressed.

It is at this point of intersection that the analysis of the term radically changes its meaning, going from one point to another, encompassing everyone without any kind of distinction, which leads us to affirm that digital illiteracy is an unprecedented reality that affects all the population, from the least formally educated to the highest academic degrees. And it is at this point of conflict that the concern with the digital literacy process of future generations arises, understanding that being literate includes becoming literate and, for that, it is necessary to have direct contact with the object and when there are trainer teachers who are not literate digitally, for the most diverse reasons and which, to make matters worse, show resistance to the process and to ICTs, because they feel incapable of learning and mastering the pragmatic contents and tools, instill this [their] mechanism of resistance *in* students, making it even more difficult for public authorities to overcome the problem and through the application of effective action policies.

Taking this line of analysis, it appears that the proposal for overcoming the problem would be to promote an efficient continuing education of teachers, in order to provide them with the necessary knowledge to face the digital/virtual world, making pragmatic use, in the classroom. classroom, digital tools and active methodologies.

To believe in the naive idea that by distributing computers, *tablets* and *notebooks* for free, you are contributing to the eradication of digital illiteracy is to be completely out of objective reality, because this has already been tested, in a network and who was digitally illiterate it continued as it was and donated or sold its computers and other tools; so that it is necessary to think about strategies in which teachers are didactically inserted in the process of accessing computer networks and feel motivated to teach how to handle ICT tools.

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